

DEVELOPING MULTIFILAMENT DRAWING FACILITIES FOR PHOSPHATE GLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Phosphate glass fibres are high strength, high modulus resorbable materials with the potential for use in medical devices both in the form of textiles and as reinforcing fibres for resorbable composites. Existing production methods are limited to laboratory based single filament systems, which produce material unsuited to downstream processing. This paper describes an apparatus that has been developed to produce multi-filament, melt-drawn phosphate glass fibre. The core of the system is an electrically heated platinum alloy bushing with the capacity for the continuous introduction of glass feedstock. Threads consisting of 8 filaments were drawn successfully and continuously, bound together with a polymer sizing solution. Conditions were tuned to provide individual filament diameters of less than 20 microns, which is suitable for use as a composite reinforcing fibre. These threads were hand woven into the weft in a section of 1581 8 shaft satin weave E-glass of nominal 200 gsm weight, to provide a proof of concept woven textile form of phosphate glass fibres.

1 INTRODUCTION

Although they have their roots in optical systems, phosphate glass fibres have been in development as materials for medical applications for a number of years[1-3]. They have potential for use both directly and as reinforcement fibres in resorbable composite devices since they are of relatively high strength (typically 500 MPa to 1.2 GPa[4]) but will also degrade away in water over time. Their rate of degradation can be adjusted dramatically through changes in formulation[5], providing a versatile material type.

While there are many publications on phosphate glasses as medical materials, there are relatively few on phosphate glass fibres and none on phosphate glass textiles. This is due to the difficulty in making fibres from these glasses in any significant quantity, largely because of their viscosity profiles. Producing an optical fibre of several 10s of microns can be achieved by pre-form drawing[6] – the stretching of a softened glass rod to reduce the diameter by a factor of around 1000. However, for fibres suitable for textile production and composite reinforcement smaller fibres are needed – less than 25 microns and preferably around 9-12 microns[7]. This is very challenging to the point of impossible for pre-form drawing and scaling pre-form drawing from a single filament to the several thousand necessary for yarn production also presents significant difficulties.

Conventional reinforcement glass fibres such as E-glass are made commercially via a melt-drawing process[8], where a stream of molten glass is passed through a precious metal bushing to form thousands of strands that are then drawn together and coated to form a roving, which can be used as

produced or converted into yarn. To support scalable fibre and textile manufacture, phosphate glasses need to be adapted to this method of manufacture. Unfortunately, the properties of phosphate glasses present difficulties to this adaptation.

Where E-glasses are ‘strong glasses’ phosphates are fragile glasses (their viscosity changes rapidly with temperature), creating a small processing window and requiring very good process temperature control. Phosphate glasses also have very low viscosities in comparison with silicates and critically the ‘drawing point’ viscosity for glass fibre production (typically assumed to be ~ 100 Pa·s or Log_2 Pa·s[9]) usually falls below the liquidus point. This means that ordinarily the glass would crystallise at the temperature suitable for forming fibres and make melt-drawing impossible. However, a number of groups including ours have been producing phosphate glass filaments in the laboratory for many years. This is because glass that is flowing is more resistant to crystallisation, lending a kinetic stability to the process. Providing the glass is constantly moving the process can work, but if the correct conditions are not maintained crystals can nucleate and grow, eventually blocking the drawing equipment and stopping the process.

This paper reports on the progress of a project to develop a multi-filament melt drawing process for phosphate glass fibres and the early stage textiles produced using these fibres.

2 FIBRE TOWER DEVELOPMENT

Existing fibre drawing facilities for phosphate glass via a melt-drawing process are typically single filament devices using a furnace to heat a crucible and relying on conduction and glass flow to provide heat to the drawing tips (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Schematic of a bulk-heated phosphate fibre production facility.

The lack of direct control of the drawing tip temperature makes it very difficult to draw multiple filaments at once. The startup process is also very slow and the nature of the heating process means that time lag when adjusting temperature is considerable. This results in a large amount of waste both in terms of glass and energy. However, once conditions are determined for a given glass formulation, reasonably reliable production of single filaments is possible.

Moving to a multiple filament drawing system requires much greater control of temperature, particularly at the drawing tips. It is also important to have a much more responsive temperature control to allow tuning to conditions. This can be achieved through direct electrical resistance heating. Careful design of a precious metal (usually a platinum/rhodium alloy) drawing bushing ensures heating of specific areas and responsive control of the drawing tips (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Example of a commercial electrically heated glass fibre bushing

Through consultation with expert bushing and tower manufacturers and electrical specialists, a pilot scale drawing tower was designed and built in place at the premises of Glass Technology Services Ltd. This incorporated a 10 drawing tip electrically heated bushing system using a water cooled RoMan transformer and busbars and a Eurotherm control system, a custom built fibre coating system and a Controls Interfaces tower frame and traversing take up wheel with adjustable speed and pitch. It was produced with variable cooling capability, adjustable heating contacts to control the temperature profile on the bushing and the capacity for continuous introduction of feedstock glass.

The temperature of the bushing was measured at two points for control, with the resulting PID 4-20mA hard-wired output fed to a single phase Epower thyristor controller, which in turn drove the primary of a high-current bushing transformer. The transformer converted the applied mains voltage at the primary winding to a few volts at thousands of amps at the secondary winding, to feed through the very low impedance busbars to the bushing and heat the glass contained within. Three additional thermocouples provided information on the temperature across the bushing.

Cooling could be controlled by the placement of water cooled copper fins between the drawing tips and a screen in the loading chute ensured that pieces of feedstock glass introduced to the bushing would melt and not fall to the bottom and block the drawing tips. Airflow around the bushing was minimised to improve thermal stability. The completed system is shown in Fig. 3

Figure 3: Installed pilot scale multifilament melt-drawing system showing the bushing and transformer system on top of the tower, the winder and the control box (coating system not shown)

3 GLASS FEEDSTOCK CHOICE

Previous work on phosphate glasses at the University of Nottingham has established a wide range of phosphate glass formulations, the majority of which can be converted into fibres by using the single filament drawing system (see Fig. 1). In order to have the best chance of success in the multifilament drawing process, a thermal and viscosity study of a range of candidate glasses was undertaken (reported elsewhere[10]) and the glass with lowest fragility selected. Initially this was an iron containing glass but subsequently an iron free formulation was chosen as it was determined that the coloured iron containing glass cooled too rapidly for effective fibre drawing. The primary glass used for the process was of the composition 55 mol% P_2O_5 , 24 mol% MgO , 16 mol% CaO and 5 mol% Na_2O .

4 FIBRE PRODUCTION

Fibre production was successful with it being possible to draw 8 filaments continuously. It was not possible to draw all 10 at once due to difficulties in achieving a consistent temperature across the entire bushing. The 8 filaments were successfully bound into threads by using a polymer-based sizing solution applied during production. Initial trials produced filaments with diameters on the order of 40 microns and so diameter optimisation was necessary. Even at this size the fibres demonstrated good Weibull strength (550 MPa) and modulus (10.15), which was promising for the process.

To optimise for fibre diameter, the bushing temperature and the winding speed of the 1m circumference collection drum were varied as shown in Fig. 4. Sub 20 micron fibres could be obtained continuously with relative ease and could be pushed to 10 microns for short periods.

Figure 4: Variation in fibre diameter of continuously produced filaments as a function of temperature and winding speed (measured using SEM)

The optimised drawing conditions were used to produce a number of ordered fibre drums that were transported to Valmiera's site for textile production trials.

5 TEXTILE PRODUCTION

The threads passed to Valmiera were too fine for use in machine driven textile manufacture but were used successfully in a manual process. The threads were hand woven as the weft in a section of 1581 8 shaft satin weave E-glass of nominal 200 gsm weight, with a thread count of 22.5/cm for the warp and 21/cm for the weft. The resulting fabric is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Section of handwoven phosphate glass thread in an E-glass weft

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study has demonstrated that a multifilament phosphate glass fibre melt-drawing process is possible and that threads produced in this way can be woven into a fabric. Appropriate scale up of the process should enable the production of threads that are sufficiently robust to enable the production of pure phosphate glass fibre textiles.

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